

ABSTRACT TERMS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE: LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CONSIDERATIONS

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Abstract: The subject of the study is the socio-cultural peculiarity of neonomination in the English and Uzbek languages; the target of the study is the neologisms of the literary English of the last three decades at the turn of the XX-XXI centuries. While the majority of studies in this vein focus on languages with different systems, in our study, languages that belong to the same language group are analyzed in a comparative manner. The reason for these languages' contacts is that their speakers share many cultural and historical ties. The purpose of the work is to identify ways to reflect the interaction of language and culture, language and society in the neologisms of the English and Uzbek languages, as well as to analyze the changes that the Uzbek language has undergone under the influence of global English.

Keywords: cultural linguistics / abstract nouns / concept / linguo-cultureme / synonyms / realities.

One of the most fascinating and challenging lexeme groups to study is abstract nouns. Researchers examining this category of nouns will certainly run into issues with clearly defining the concept itself, differentiating between abstract and concrete nouns, and dealing with the intricate following classification of abstract names. Furthermore, the nature of abstraction is contentious. As a result, scientists have attempted to determine the circumstances in which an individual's and/or society's capacity for abstraction emerges, as well as the corresponding category of names in the language, at different points in time and from the perspectives of various linguistic disciplines.

Defining the terms "abstraction" and "abstract name" is one of the hardest things linguists have to do. Although the categories of abstract and concrete nouns can be distinguished intuitively, a precise and clear separation between them has not yet been established because the researcher's perspective greatly influences how this boundary is understood.

Before considering various approaches to understanding the name of the abstract, let's turn to the origins of the term. In philosophy, the term "abstraction" (from Latin *abstractio* - distraction) was introduced by Boethius as a translation of the term used by Aristotle. At the same time, the abstract is understood as an abstract property of an object, in contrast to a specific name denoting the object itself. The issue of distinguishing between the abstract and the concrete, as well as understanding the

essence of abstraction as a process and result of cognition, was touched upon by the Socrates Antisthenes and Aristippus, later by Plato (primarily in the dialogue Theaetetus) and Aristotle (for example, Metaphysics, On Interpretation). Recognizing the existence of both objects in the field of sensible perceived and intelligible things, philosophers disagree in understanding the latter - while Plato believed that general, universal "kinds and types" are not only thought separately from material objects, but also exist independently outside of them, Aristotle believed that abstract concepts and representations exist in concrete objects, and are only thought separately.

Boethius, on the other hand, turned to the problem of abstractions, reflecting on the problem of universals in his Commentary on Porphyry, translated by himself. Despite the fact that Porphyry himself only outlined the problematic of "forms of incorporeal things" (namely, whether they exist in connection with bodies or have an independent existence), emphasizing that this issue is too complex and deep, in a commentary on his works, Boethius considers this the problem in detail. Paying attention to the ability of a person to think and "divide" (or abstract), he writes: "... the spirit, endowed with the ability to bind the disconnected, and the connection to decompose, so dismembers the things transferred to it, confused by feelings and connected by bodies, that they appear before him for consideration on their own in their incorporeal nature, separate from the bodies with which they have grown together" (Boethius 1991, 26-27). So, for example, people are able to distinguish common features and properties of dissimilar objects and designate abstract concepts "mixed with bodies" (the thinker gives an example of a line that does not exist separately from the body, nevertheless, a person is able to represent it separately). Thus, Boethius distinguishes three categories of childbirth - "corporal", i.e. existing substantially, and "incorporeal", in turn subdivided into existing independently of bodies (for example, mind, soul) and not dependent on and connected with the body (for example, line, surface).

Throughout the 20th century, new works on social stratification appeared. On the one hand, the researchers sought to define the concept; although their understanding of the social class was different: the class was considered as a historical phenomenon (E.P. Thompson), as a phenomenon at the intersection of economics, politics and public life (K. Polanyi). On the other hand, sociologists paid attention to the change in the structure of society from the time of Marx to the time of their work. So, R. Dahrendorf in his work "Class and class struggle in an industrial society" speaks of the emergence of many new classes (capitalists, heirs of the state, managers and others). It is necessary to take into account the fact that most works on the class are primarily devoted to the study of the working class, which has undergone significant changes since the beginning of the 20th century: working and living conditions have improved, which partly destroyed the usual cohesion of this community; there were opportunities to get

an education and change the scope of employment. All this allowed researchers to declare the bourgeoisization of the working class (J. Goldthorpe, D. Lockwood). However, when talking about the improvement of the life of the working class, it is important to take into account the changes in society as a whole, as the living and working conditions of the middle class also became better, and the way of life changed; consequently, there was no fundamental change in the structure of society or individual classes.

For the correct positioning of an individual in a community, all components must be taken into account; for example, P. Bourdieu noted the difference in sports hobbies, emphasizing that the upper strata of society were constantly looking for new types of activity as some sports became available to the masses. Therefore, such sports as, for example, golf, tennis, fencing, yachting, show jumping, became popular in high society. classes, as a rule, do not involve team play, requiring relatively little physical effort, but significant investments. "Thus it is noticeable that economic barriers, whatever they may be in the case of golf, skiing, even horseback riding or tennis, cannot alone explain the class stratification in the practice of these sports. There are many other, hidden, requirements for participation, such as family tradition and childhood training, required manners (both behavior and appearance) and a special form of communication that close these sports to the working class..." (Bourdieu 1984, 214). Accordingly, when distinguishing classes, the author proposes to take into account both the economic component and social and cultural capital. Three decades later, this theory was used in the Great British Class Survey, designed to compile a new classification of social classes. The study will be described in more detail below.

In modern neology, a linguoculturological approach is promising, from the standpoint of which neologisms are considered as units with culturally significant information. This approach is based on the position that neologisms are the result of human activity and may have a cultural load. The need to develop a linguocultural approach is dictated by the fact that the content of neologisms is formed under the influence of not only linguistic, but also cultural factors.

The chronological criterion is one of the fundamental ones in the linguoculturological approach in neology. A language unit can be classified as "new" only at a certain time interval. So, for example, we can talk about the neologisms of the turn of the millennium (Dutch globofob - anti-globalist; English eurosphere - the territory of member countries / candidates for the European Union) or neologisms of the 40s. 20th century (Dutch 'holocaust'; English 'genocide'), etc.

Within the framework of the linguoculturological approach, we study neologisms from the standpoint of the following methods:

1) diachronic analysis, which involves the study of a neological unit in time; it applies primarily to semantic neologisms, previously known words that have taken on

new meanings (Uzbek 'marafon' or "event of a long duration"; English lobby "hallway" or "a group of persons promoting a bill");

2) contrastive analysis, which makes it possible to reveal the cultural specificity of neologism through its systemic comparison with neologism that has the same meaning or denotes the same reality in another language. For example, the English unit 'meanwhile' matches its Uzbek equivalent 'ayni paytda' only in the first meaning "meanwhile". In English, this unit has become a semantic neologism and acquired the second meaning "minor news";

3) definitional analysis, which makes it possible to reveal the cultural specificity of neologism when studying its dictionary definition.

4) conceptual analysis, which involves, in particular, the construction of a lexico-semantic field, which allows distributing the units under study into conceptual spheres and reconstructing the neological lexico-semantic field of a particular conceptual category. For example, the category "human relationships" is verbalized in English by a large number of neologisms denoting the active use of technical means of communication: Skype sleep "to fall asleep together with the Skype program (Skype) turned on"; website "a site where a young couple posts information about their upcoming wedding"; virtual visitation "virtual visit, contact of a divorced parent with his child using electronic means of communication", etc.

An analysis of the factual material, taking into account the criteria and methods of the linguoculturological approach in neology, made it possible to establish that the categories of neologisms with the most pronounced national and cultural marking include semantic neologisms (new words that have received additional lexico-semantic variants (LSV) in the process of their development and have sociocultural connotations), lexical neologisms denoting new realities, which can be both universal and specific to one culture, as well as phraseological neologisms, due to the idiomatic nature of their meaning.

The national and cultural marking of language innovations is also revealed in the course of the analysis of the system of meanings of new words and their combinations into lexico-semantic paradigms. The interaction of language and culture is manifested in the way new lexical units are distributed over various conceptual spheres in different languages. The dominance of this or that sphere, characterized by active processes of neologization, illustrates the fact that the nomination of new realities and the generation of new meanings takes place taking into account the value orientations of the language community and is a consequence of the interaction of linguistic and cultural pictures of the world.

In English, the identified conceptual areas with the largest number of neologisms include: the sphere "society and man", "man and culture", "technology and science",

"economics and business"; – in Uzbek: “social policy”, “computer technology and the Internet”, “economy”, “ecology and environment”.

By putting particular state language policy measures into place, including creating a linguistic counseling program, the national language can be shielded from the damaging effects of globalization. The creation of communicative speech norms is another method. The creation of specialized professionally guided dictionaries that would set language standards for members of particular professions—teachers, doctors, attorneys, etc.—rather than for all native speakers is a useful idea. In addition, as ecolinguistics is a scientific field with the ability to balance national and global languages, it is critical to advance ecolinguistics as a field of study and to put the findings of ecolinguistic research to use in practice.

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